

SnakeCube: containerized and automated pipeline for *de novo* genome assembly in HPC environments

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Abstract

Summary: The rapid progress in sequencing technology and related bioinformatics tools is leading to disentangling diversity and conservation issues through genome analyses. The foremost challenges of the field involve coping with questions emerging from the swift development and application of new algorithms, as well as the establishment of standardized analysis approaches that promote transparency and transferability in research. Here, we present SnakeCube, a containerized whole genome assembly pipeline that runs within isolated, secured environments and scales for use in HPC domains.

Availability: SnakeCube is available via an open source license at GitHub: <https://github.com/genomenerds/SnakeCube>

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1. Introduction

Modern sequencing technologies allow scientists to generate *de novo* genome sequences for non-model organisms. However, implementing such bioinformatics analyses is challenging for both human and non-human resources, in any experimental and scientific environment. The time consumed for manually controlling and pairing computationally heavy and memory straining tasks, highlight the need for automation aiming at the standardization and chaining of the steps involved.

Most existing workflows refer to the containerization of a single tool, may not involve automation, or containerization, making application in high performance computing (HPC) environments hard (Leprevost *et al.*, 2017, Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2019). Following the needs of the community, we aimed at building a pipeline which perform analyses from start (raw data) to end (fully polished assembly) in an automated manner and in a containerized form for use in HPC domains. We built Snakecube, a *de novo* genome assembly pipeline, which takes advantage of both long MinION and short Illumina

reads. The workflow is based on our previous work on *Lagocephalus sceleratus* genome (Danis *et al.*, 2020) and is benchmarked and optimized using two extra datasets, highlighting the response of the software given various inputs.

2. Methods

The pipeline was constructed using the Snakemake workflow manager, (Koster & Rahmann, 2012) and isolated in a Singularity container for autonomy and integrity (Kurtzer *et al.*, 2017). The container image runs as a single job in any linux-kernel based system and each of its steps (rules) is performed into a unique Conda environment (Anaconda Software Distribution, 2020) with pre-installed tools. In such environments, the user has full control while not granted elevated privileges on the host system. This feature makes the rather useful containers suitable for exploitation in multi-user domains, where safety issues are of high priority. The users have control over their analysis through a set of hyper-parameters declared in an external configuration file, which controls variables of the included applications. All results are saved into the user's workspace, along with a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of the steps and a summary file with the status of the output files for validation.

3. Results

SnakeCube was first evaluated for its efficiency by comparing its output with the initial *L. sceleratus* analysis (Danis *et al.*, 2020), with which it scored similar statistics (Table 1). Then, the tool was benchmarked for its cpu load and memory usage while running serially, and optimized for its speed and resource handling by introducing parallel rule execution. The benefits of parallel execution and the general performance of SnakeCube was tested using two additional datasets of different organisms, to cover a range of genome sizes, raw data sizes and taxonomic groups: Caddisfly (insect) (Heckenhauer *et al.*, 2019) and Crane (bird) (Zhou *et al.*, 2019).

3.1 Benchmarking and Optimization

Cpu load and memory usage analysis (Fig.1a) indicated no sign of overloading. Even during the execution of demanding rules (see Supplementary Material), the system reported idle cpus, and the memory usage was always lower than the given limit (128GB RAM). The parallelization was introduced by dynamically determining the minimum threads needed for each rule to reach its maximum computing-scaling efficiency (Fig.1b). By gradually adding cpus and re-running each step, the point beyond which the addition did not decrease the rule's execution time (Time vs Threads curve flattens), was considered optimum. The unused cpus were then given to

speed up other, independent rules. The time optimization accomplished is data-specific and fluctuates from 10% to 20% (see Supplementary Material).

a) Benchmarking SnakeCube

b) Optimization of multithreading for Rules

Fig. 1 a) Benchmarking the Snakemake rules for CPU Load and USS memory usage. Each point is the average of each rule given 20 CPUs for running. Memory USS is reported in MB and Time in seconds. b) Determining the optimum number of cpus per rule. The multiq_c and multiq_c_t rules are omitted due to their insignificant complexity.

3.2 Performance estimation

After benchmarking and optimizing SnakeCube, its final performance evaluation was based on the assemblies completeness (Simão *et al.*, 2015) and time efficiency (Table 1).

Table 1. SnakeCube's performance

Dataset	Raw-data size	Genome Size Estimation	Busco C%	Published Busco C%	Execution Time
<i>Hydropsyche tenuis</i>	8.3Gb MinION, 18.8Gb Illumina paired-end	219Mb	98.2%	98.3%	35h26m
<i>L. sceleratus</i>	9.68GB MinION, 17,19Gb Illumina paired- end	373Mb	96.7%	96.2%	27h29m
<i>Grus nigricollis</i>	116.5Gb MinION, 54.6 Illumina paired-end	1.23Gb	94.7%	97.7%	7d04h47m

4. Conclusion

Overall, SnakeCube is robust and capable of accomplishing as good results as in the original analyses, saving both time and effort. The performance varies, as expected, for different types of datasets and organisms, but is generally notably high, making SnakeCube a fine candidate for use in future research.

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